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CONTENTS

Land Surrender and Post-Surrender Problems in Buea Sub-Division: The Case of Muea Court Area.....1

Impact of the Crisis in Cameroon’s North West and South West Regions on Business Organizations: The case of Cameroon Development Corporation (CDC) and Groupe Fokou (FK).....19

The Effect of Project Governance Structure on Project Success in Medino Bamenda, Northwest Region Cameroon.....32

The Effect of Project Governance Structure on Project Success in Medino Bamenda, Northwest Region Cameroon

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Abstract

The main aim of the study is to examine the effect of project governance structure on project success in Medino Bamenda. This study employs the quantitative research design. Among the target population of this study is constituted of people working in Medino. Using the Yamane formula, a sample size of 73 workers was selected through purposive sampling. The ordinary least square technique was used to estimate the regression. The findings from objective one shows that project steering committee has a positive but insignificant effect on project process. The finding from objective two shows that project manager has a positive but insignificant effect on project process and retains the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect between project manager and project success in Medino, Bamenda. Findings in objective 3 shows that project resource allocation has a positive and significant effect on project process and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant effect between project steering committee and project success of Medino in Bamenda. The study recommends that effective managing and allocating resources, such as personnel, equipment, and funding, is crucial for the project's success. Also it is recommended to ensure that the project manager has the necessary skills, experience, and authority to lead the project, provide them with the necessary resources and support, establish clear communication channels and decision-making processes, and consider providing the project manager with additional training or mentorship to enhance their project management capabilities. Therefore, it is concluded from findings that the effect of project governance structure has a positive effect on project success in Medino, Bamenda.

Keywords: Project Management, Project steering, Resource, Project Manager, Project success

1. Introduction

Project governance structure plays an important role in determining project success, especially in complex and dynamic environments like Mideno Bamenda. MIDENO – the Mission for the Development of the North West Region, is a government organization responsible for driving development in the Region through economic growth, infrastructure improvement, and social welfare initiatives. With a professional team comprising project managers, engineers, economists, and community development specialists, the authority identifies regional needs, develops strategic

plans, and executes projects across key sectors such as agriculture, industry, and infrastructure. By supporting modern farming practices, promoting industrialization, and constructing essential facilities like roads, schools, and health centres, Mideno aims to transform the Northwest Region into a thriving hub of economic and social progress. Given the scale and complexity of Mideno's development activities, effective project governance is crucial for ensuring successful project delivery. Good governance enhances project management, strengthens accountability, promotes risk mitigation, and ensures stakeholder satisfaction. In the context of an organization like Mideno Bamenda, a well-defined governance structure can significantly improve project outcomes and the overall achievement of development goals.

Recent studies (Roijsackers, 2009; Osipova & Eriksson, 2013) have demonstrated that strong project governance is positively correlated with project success, particularly when it incorporates a stakeholder-oriented approach. Muller (2009) further emphasizes that governance frameworks are vital in ensuring projects are executed efficiently and remain aligned with organizational objectives. When organizations implement clear governance processes, they often experience greater transparency, effective resource utilisation, and enhanced accountability.

Despite the critical role of project governance in determining project success, many projects in complex environments like Mideno Bamenda face significant challenges due to inadequate governance structures.

Consequently, there is a compelling need to comprehensively investigate the role of project governance structures, including steering committees, project managers, and resource management, in influencing project success within the Mideno Bamenda context. By addressing this critical knowledge void, this research aims to provide actionable insights that can empower Mideno Bamenda to enhance its project management strategies, allocate resources judiciously, and ensure the achievement of project objectives, ultimately contributing to the organization's overall success.

2. Literature Review

1. Conceptual Literature Review

Project Governance

Project governance is a critical aspect of project management that focuses on the mechanisms and structures used to guide and control projects (Crawford, 2005). It involves the allocation of decision-making authority, the establishment of accountability, and the implementation of processes and procedures to ensure project success (Pinto, 2015). Effective project governance is essential for ensuring that projects are aligned with organizational objectives and strategic priorities (Crawford, 2005). It provides a framework for decision-making, risk management, and resource allocation, enabling stakeholders to have a clear understanding of project progress and outcomes (Pinto, 2015).

Project Manager

A project manager is an individual who is responsible for the planning, execution, and successful completion of a project. They are the key point of contact and the driving force behind the project, ensuring that all aspects of the project are well-coordinated and aligned with the project goals. The role of a project manager is crucial in ensuring the successful execution and completion of projects (Kerzner, 2017). A project manager

is responsible for planning, organizing, and controlling all aspects of a project, from initiation to closure (Cleland & Ireland, 2004).

Project Steering Committee

The concept of a project steering committee is an integral part of project governance and management. A project steering committee is a group of individuals responsible for providing guidance, oversight, and decision-making authority for a project (Kerzner, 2017). It serves as a crucial governance mechanism to ensure that the project remains aligned with organizational objectives and strategic priorities (Crawford, 2005).

The primary role of a project steering committee is to set the overall direction and priorities for the project. They provide strategic guidance and ensure that the project objectives are in line with the organization's goals (Kerzner, 2017). The committee approves project plans, budgets, and resources, and ensures that the project remains on track to deliver the intended outcomes (Crawford, 2005). Overall, the concept of a project steering committee is instrumental in driving successful project execution and achieving desired outcomes.

Project Resource Allocation

Certainly, project resource allocation is a critical aspect of project management that involves the strategic distribution and utilization of resources to ensure the successful execution of a project (Kerzner, 2017). It involves identifying and assigning the necessary personnel, budget, equipment, and other resources to specific tasks and activities within the project (Cleland & Ireland, 2004). The allocation of resources in a project is essential to optimize efficiency, productivity, and overall project success. It requires careful planning and consideration of the project's requirements, constraints, and objectives (Kerzner, 2017). By allocating resources effectively, project managers can ensure that the right resources are available at the right time, in the right quantities, and in the right areas of the project.

One of the key considerations in project resource allocation is identifying the skills and expertise required for each task or activity within the project. This involves assessing the project's needs and matching them with the capabilities and availability of the project team members (Cleland & Ireland, 2004). By allocating resources based on their strengths and competencies, project managers can enhance team performance and productivity.

Project Success

A few decades ago, project management (PM) has become the most widely used management model in organizations (Huemann et al., 2017). Hence, this situation arises because one has to manage his project to succeed in a complex and problematic environment (Gemün den et al., 2018). While the Project Management Institute has developed a technical model for successful project management (PMI, 2013), the International Project Management Association has also established a comprehensive competence baseline to guide project management practice (Loufrani-Fedida & Missonier, 2015). As a result, the success of a project depends on the project managers who portray leadership skills and use them to form a project management team and openly lead the team to meet project management requirements during implementation phases (Dow & Taylor, 2015).

Conceptual Framework

This framework focuses on the direct relationships between the independent variables (project governance elements) and the dependent variable (project success), with a specific emphasis on how they influence project outcomes in Mideno Bamenda, Cameroon.

2. Theoretical Literature Review

Rational Choice Theory (Coleman et al., 1940s)

According to Dowding (2011), rational choice incorporates the behaviour of people in terms of their preferences within a formal structure. Through organizing perspective methodology models are built around the non-predictability of politics, commitments, democratic conflicts and anomalies around principle-agent theory. Of note, and very relevant to governance approaches, is the finding by McClennen (1997) that through pragmatic rationality and rules, commitment is bound by consequentialism. This finding is supported by Dietrich and List (2013) that someone's preferences, or eventual commitments, may vary with changes in individual's or organizations' motivating reasons. Eventually, governance should aim to provide normative reasons or motivations to provide a point of reference. The contribution of rational choice theory towards governance, lies in the awareness of the dangers of regulation when agencies capture the regulators for their own interest. In such cases the inefficiencies and inequities could be devastating to other interest groups (Dowding, 2011).

Principle-Agent and Transaction Cost Theories (Michael Jensen and William Meckling, 1976)

The basic formation of principle-agent theory takes place when delegation occurs when the agent has time, information, resources and skills that the principle lacks (Kiewiet & McCubbins, 1991). Due to this mutually dependent relationship principle-agent theory is entrenched in commitment problems. The dilemma of fairness, incentives, compensation and acting in the general *esprit de corps* of the overall objectives, remains complicated and often illusive. Viewing projects as temporary organizations the principle-agent theory also transpires in the project world, thereby transcending the principles of the underlying theories of governance towards project actors (Turner & Müller, 2003). Extending principle agent theory to transaction cost theory the terms services provider and customer emerge, thereby entrenching the commercial relationship as evident in most agreements (Frauendorf, 2006). Turner and Keegan (2001) incorporated transaction theory into a governance mechanism for project, by referring to the roles of the 'broker' and 'steward'.

It can be argued that governance is globally maturing. Various mechanisms have been developed to measure governance. These measurements assess the overall public health of nations by addressing and valuing liberal democracy, constitutional democracy, level of good governance, corruption and human rights (Norris, 2011). With the theory and principles of governance generally agreed upon, various countries embarked on their own efforts to transform the principles into practice by developing and establishing their internal corporate or organizational governance frameworks or models.

3. Empirical Literature Review

Jan Terje Karlsen's (2020) study on project steering committees, project governance, and trust is important as it highlights how leaders possess the authority to make decisions that directly affect project outcomes. He also explains that the steering committees provides strategic directions and governance for projects and they support the project manager. The paper provides key managerial implications that project owners should take into account when organizing a steering committee. The analysis identifies composition, competence, authority, responsibility, commitment and continuity as steering committee features that contribute to building trust. Findings particularly highlight the choice to include external steering committee members to be successful. Alvarenga et al. (2018) review the experts involved in project management to assess the importance of project managers to the success of the project. The end realistic result is that project managers must be aware of the awareness and commitment and the next pressure to maintain mental and emotional health under the pressure of continued success.

Henkel et al. (2019) explore Job leadership and relationships, investigate leadership behaviour to find out how leadership behaviour relates to the performance of a project manager in a project team that is critical to the success of a project. Leadership skills and styles can be learned based on a high level of understanding and self-esteem, which are key factors in project success. It provides the skills to work with project management leaders, especially the ability to motivate, motivate and lead project teams. Ndayisaba and Mulyungi (2018) worked on the management of resources and the implementation of projects. Project to Strengthen Livelihoods in Rural Rwanda Time management, financial resources, and human resources were all used to assess resource allocation. All project participants were included in the target population. Analysis of data was quantitatively done through regression analysis so as to assess how the variables under study were related to one another. It was discovered that management of resources accounted for 83.7% influence on successful implementation of projects in strengthening livelihoods in rural Rwanda project Muhanga district.

Kimutai and Kirui (2020) investigated the impact of resource schedule on the implementation of residential building projects in Kenya. Task allocation and time management were used to assess resource allocation. The design employed was descriptive research. The population constituted of 79 residential projects and the respondents were the project managers, project supervisors, and contractors. Questionnaires were used in collecting data. The study discovered a link between resource scheduling and project implementation.

Ochieng (2018) investigated the impact of resource management on the implementation of mobile communications companies' projects in Kenya. Task scheduling and time allocation were used to assess resource management. The target population consisted of fifty project team members from Kenya's four major GSM companies. To demonstrate the relationship between the variables, descriptive statistics were used. The study also revealed that technology is still poorly managed, with a large proportion of respondents indicating that databases are managed manually and project management software is rarely used.

4. Research Gap

The research gap lies in the need for a detailed and context-specific examination of how project governance structures and practices interact with the unique socio-economic, cultural, and political landscape of Mideno Bamenda in Cameroon. Addressing this gap is essential to provide practical insights and recommendations for improving project success in this particular setting. This study aims to bridge this research gap by conducting an in-depth investigation of project governance and its effect on project success in Mideno Bamenda, ultimately contributing to the body of knowledge in project management within the African context.

3. Methodology

1. Research Design

This study employs a quantitative research approaches to comprehensively examine the effects of project governance on project success in the specific context of Mideno Bamenda, Cameroon. This research used descriptive statistics and Pearson Chi-Square to analyse the research objectives.

The population of the study comprises all the workers of Medino in the North West Region of Bamenda, Cameroon. As of the most recent data available, the total population of Mideno in this region is reported to be 89 individuals. These individuals encompass a diverse range of roles and responsibilities within the Medino community, including members of the project steering committee, project managers, and various stakeholders involved in resource allocation and budget control.

2. Sampling Technique and Size

A purposive sampling strategy will be employed to select participants, ensuring representation from diverse project roles and perspectives. The sample will include members of the project steering committee, project managers, and other stakeholders involved in resource allocation and budget control. The primary source of quantitative data will be the workers of Medino Bamenda, particularly those directly involved in project governance structures.

The sample size for this study is determined to be 73 individuals, drawn from the overall population of 89 workers in Mideno, North West Region, Bamenda. The sample size for the study was selected using the Yamane (1967) formula for calculating sample size for a finite sample to be as seen below;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)} \text{ Equation 1}$$

Where: n is the sample size, N is the population size (89). e is the precision level (expressed as a decimal).

$$n = \frac{89}{1 + 89(0.05)^2}, \quad n = \frac{89}{1 + 89(0.0025)}, \quad n = \frac{89}{1.2225} \quad n = 72.8016 = 73$$

3. Model Specification

$$PS = \beta_0 + \beta_1PSC + \beta_2PRA + \beta_4PM + \varepsilon$$

PS= Project Success

β_0 =Beta constant

β_1 - β_4 = Represent the regression coefficient

PSC= Project Steering Committee

PRA= Project Resource Allocation

PM= Project Manager

ε =Error term

Validity of Study

This study adopted a content validity. An instrument content validity is effectively enhanced through specialist ruling. For this research, content validity was ensured by subjecting the questionnaires to a panel of peers to make sure that each question is convenient with the objectives and addresses the research question correctly.

Reliability of Instruments

The Cronbach's alpha (a), which was created using the internal consistency technique, was used to make sure that the instrument has perfect internal consistence and to measure the underlying construct reliability. Reliability coefficient of 0.7 was used in this study as a role of thumb to signify a satisfactory level of consistency.

4. Ethical Consideration

Respecting the autonomy and privacy of the participants was crucial, and their personal information was handled securely and confidentially.

4. Results and Discussion of Findings

1. Reliability Statistics with help of Cronbach's Alpha

Table 1: Reliability Statistics with help of Cronbach's Alpha

Items	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Project success	.850
Project Steering Committee	.817
Project Manager	.831
Project Resource Allocation	.818
Cronbach's Alpha Value	.866

Source: Author (2025)

From the table above, it shows that the data can be reliable this is because the total Cronbach alpha value for the variables, for all the 4 items is 0.866 which is greater than 0.7, hence our analysis can be reliable.

2. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	(Skewness)	(Kurtosis)
PS	73	19.726	3.724	10	25	0.003	0.566
PSC	73	19.233	3.784	11	25	0.035	0.055
PM	73	19.288	3.51	11	25	0.107	0.505
RA	73	19.37	3.165	12	24	0.001	0.590
Male	73	.548	.501	0	1	0.469	0.000
Married	73	.644	.482	0	1	0.032	0.000
Single	73	.274	.449	0	1	0.001	0.004
Primary Edu	73	.055	.229	0	1	0.000	0.000
Secondary Edu	73	.219	.417	0	1	0.000	0.967
Tertiary Edu	73	.712	.456	0	1	0.002	0.000
Longevity 5-9years	73	.342	.478	0	1	0.019	0.000
Longevity Age 10-14years	73	.37	.486	0	1	0.052	0.000
Longevity Age 15years +	73	.178	.385	0	1	0.000	0.113

Source: Author (2025)

The high mean of 19.726 for project success (PS) suggests that, on average, the projects undertaken in Bamenda by Miden0 have been relatively successful. This could be indicative of effective project management practices, strong stakeholder engagement, and the successful delivery of project outcomes. The standard deviation of 3.724 indicates a moderate level of variability in the project success scores. This suggests that while most projects have achieved a relatively high level of success, there may be some variation in the performance of individual projects. The standard deviation provides an indication of the spread or dispersion of the project success scores.

More so, the mean of 19.233 for the project steering committee (PSC) variable suggests that, on average, the project steering committees in Miden0's projects have been relatively effective in supporting project success. This could be attributed to factors such as the composition of the committee, the level of engagement and oversight, and the decision-making processes within the committee. The standard deviation of 3.784 indicates a moderately high level of variability in the effectiveness of the project steering committees across different projects. This suggests that while the steering committees have generally been effective, there may be some variation in their performance and influence on project success.

Furthermore, the mean of 19.37 for project resource allocation (RA) suggests that, on average, the allocation and utilization of resources (financial, human, and material) in Miden0's projects have been relatively effective in supporting project success. This could be indicative of sound budgeting, resource planning, and efficient resource management practices. The standard deviation of 3.165 indicates a relatively low level of variability in the effectiveness of project resource allocation across different projects.

This suggests a relatively consistent approach to resource allocation and management, which has contributed to the overall success of the projects.

In addition, the mean of 0.549 for gender indicates that, on average, the sample has a slightly higher proportion of male participants compared to female participants. This could be reflective of the gender composition within the project management teams or the broader construction industry in Bamenda. The standard deviation of 0.501 suggests a moderate level of variation in the gender distribution within the sample. This means that while the sample has a slightly higher proportion of male participants, there is still a significant presence of female participants.

Additionally, the mean of 0.645 for marital status suggests that, on average, the sample has a higher proportion of married participants compared to single participants. This could be influenced by factors such as the age distribution of the project team members or cultural norms in the Bamenda region. The standard deviation of 4.82 indicates a relatively high level of variability in the marital status distribution within the sample. This suggests that the sample includes a diverse mix of married and single individuals, with a slightly higher proportion of married participants.

1. Pairwise Correlation Results

Table 3: Pairwise Correlation Results

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
1) PS	1.000									
2) PSC	0.557	1.000								
3) PM	0.574	0.638	1.000							
4) RA	0.610	0.715	0.592	1.000						
(5) FEMALE	0.052	0.049	0.013	-0.011	1.000					
(6) MARRIED	0.084	-0.041	0.001	-0.186	0.136	1.000				
(7) T_EDU	0.362	0.177	0.451	0.210	0.187	0.033	1.000			
(8) F5_9YEARS	-0.157	-0.216	-0.084	-0.204	-	0.296	0.076	1.000		
(9)	-0.005	0.185	-0.026	0.090	0.443	-	-	-	-0.553	1.000
F10_14YEARS					0.025	0.260	0.077			
(10) F15YEARS	0.112	-0.110	0.033	-0.043	0.758	0.197	0.059	0.345	0.357	1.000

Source: Author (2025)

Project success is positively correlated with project steering committee, project manager, project resource allocation, Female, Age Group 40-49 years, Married People, Tertiary Education and Longevity (15 years and above). These positive correlations suggest that as these variables increase, project success also tends to increase. This indicates that effective project steering committees, competent project managers, and efficient resource allocation contribute to higher project success. Also, female project team members, individuals in the 40-49 age group, married individuals, and those with tertiary education and long tenures (15+ years) are associated with greater project success. However, project success is also negatively correlated with Age Group 20-39 years, Age Group 30-39 years, Longevity (5-9 years) and Longevity (10-15 years). These negative correlations suggest that as these variables increase, project success tends to decrease. This indicates that Younger project team members (20-39 years and 30-39 years) are associated with lower project success. Individuals with moderate work

experience (5-9 years and 10-15 years) are associated with lower project success compared to those with longer tenures (15+ years). The positive and negative correlations provide valuable insights into the factors that influence project success in Mideno's projects in Bamenda. The findings suggest that a combination of strong project governance structures, experienced and skilled project teams, and a diverse workforce (in terms of gender, age, and education) contribute to higher project success. These insights can be used to inform Mideno's project management practices, team composition, and professional development initiatives to enhance the overall success of their projects in the Bamenda region.

2. Linear Regression Results

Table 4: Linear Regression Results

Project success	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	Sig
PSC	.295	.339	0.87	.388	
PM	.371	.31	1.20	.235	
RA	.953	.327	2.91	.005	***
female	.554	.689	0.80	.424	
married	1.367	.792	1.73	.089	*
Tertiary Edu	1.592	.843	1.89	.063	*
F5_9years	-1.055	1.289	-0.82	.416	
F10_14years	-.446	1.152	-0.39	.7	
F15years	.14	1.406	0.10	.921	
Constant	17.963	1.188	15.13	0	***
Mean dependent var	19.726	SD dependent var	3.724		
R-squared	0.513	Number of obs	73		
F-test	7.369	Prob > F	0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	365.620	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	388.525		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Author (2025)

Table 4 shows the regression results for the variables used in the study. It shows that the positive sign on the coefficient of project steering committee (PSC) (0.295) indicates that as the effectiveness of the project steering committee increases, project success tends to increase as well. However, the magnitude of the coefficient (0.295) suggests that the effect of project steering committee on project success is relatively small in magnitude. The probability value of 0.388 is greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, indicating that the effect of project steering committee on project success is statistically insignificant. The insignificant effect of project steering committee on project success could be due to factors such as the composition of the committee, the level of engagement and oversight, or the decision-making processes within the committee. Based on the regression results, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that project steering committee has no significant effect on project success. The evidence does not provide sufficient statistical support to conclude that project steering committee has a significant influence on project success.

Also, the positive sign on the coefficient of project manager (PM) (0.371) suggests that as the effectiveness of the project manager increases, project success tends to increase as well. The magnitude of the coefficient (0.371) indicates a moderate positive effect of project manager on project success. The probability value of 0.235 is greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, indicating that the effect of project manager on project success is statistically insignificant. The insignificant effect of project manager on project success could be due to factors such as the project manager's leadership skills, communication abilities, or their ability to coordinate and manage the project team and stakeholders. Based on the regression results, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that project manager has no significant effect on project success. The evidence does not provide sufficient statistical support to conclude that project manager has a significant influence on project success.

More so, the positive sign on the coefficient of project resource allocation (0.953) indicates that as the effectiveness of project resource allocation increases, project success tends to increase as well. The magnitude of the coefficient (0.953) suggests a relatively positive effect of project resource allocation on project success. The probability value of 0.005 is less than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, indicating that the effect of project resource allocation on project success is statistically significant. The significant positive effect of project resource allocation on project success could be attributed to factors such as sound budgeting, efficient resource planning, and effective resource management practices. Based on the regression results, we can reject the null hypothesis that project resource allocation has no significant effect on project success. The evidence provides sufficient statistical support to conclude that project resource allocation has a significant positive influence on project success.

Moreover, the positive sign on the coefficient of female gender (0.554) indicates that, on average, female project team members are associated with higher project success compared to male team members. The magnitude of the coefficient (0.554) suggests a moderately strong positive effect of female gender on project success. The probability value of 0.424 is greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, indicating that the effect of female gender on project success is statistically insignificant. The insignificant effect of female gender on project success could be due to factors such as the representation of female team members, their roles and responsibilities, or the organizational culture and practices within Mideno. Based on the regression results, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that female gender has no significant effect on project success. The evidence does not provide sufficient statistical support to conclude that female gender has a significant influence on project success.

Furthermore, the positive sign on the coefficient of tertiary education (1.592) suggests that, on average, project team members with tertiary education are associated with higher project success compared to those with secondary education. The magnitude of the coefficient (1.592) indicates a moderately strong positive effect of tertiary education on project success. The probability value of 0.063 is greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, but it is relatively close to the 0.10 level, indicating that the effect of tertiary education on project success is statistically significant at a 90% confidence level. The significant positive effect of tertiary education on project success could be attributed to the advanced knowledge, skills, and problem-solving abilities that individuals with higher education bring to the project team. Based on the

regression results, we can reject the null hypothesis that tertiary education has no significant effect on project success at a 90% confidence level. The evidence provides sufficient statistical support to conclude that tertiary education has a significant positive influence on project success.

Additionally, the positive sign on the coefficient of married status (1.366) indicates that, on average, married project team members are associated with higher project success compared to unmarried team members. The magnitude of the coefficient (0.500) suggests a moderately strong positive effect of being married on project success. The probability value of 0.089 is greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, but it is relatively close to the 0.10 level, indicating that the effect of marital status on project success is statistically significant at a 90% confidence level. The significant positive effect of being married on project success could be attributed to factors such as greater emotional and social support, better work-life balance, and increased sense of responsibility among married individuals. Based on the regression results, we can reject the null hypothesis that marital status has no significant effect on project success at a 90% confidence level. The evidence provides sufficient statistical support to conclude that being married has a significant positive influence on project success.

Adjusted R-squared and F-statistic

-The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.443 indicates that the independent variables (project steering committee, project manager, project resource allocation, gender, tertiary education, and marital status) explain approximately 44.3% of the variation in the dependent variable (project success).

- The F-statistic of 7.37 with a probability value of 0.000 indicates that the overall regression model is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. This means that the independent variables collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable, project success. Hence the model can be good for policy recommendation. The adjusted R-squared and F-statistic suggest that the overall regression model is a good fit and the independent variables collectively explain a significant portion of the variation in project success. These findings highlight the importance of effective resource management, human capital development, and team composition in enhancing the success of Miden's projects in Bamenda.

3. Econometric Test Statistics

1. Ramsey reset test

Table 5: Ramsey reset test

F (3, 57)	5.78
Prob>F	0.0016

Source: Author (2025)

From the Ramsey test above it shows that there is no omission of variables this is because the calculated statistical value (F-test) is greater than the probability value.

2. Breusch began/cook Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Table 6: Breusch began/cook Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Chi2(1)	0.12
Prob>chi2	0.7278

Source: Author (2025)

For heteroskedasticity, since the probability value is bigger than the chi2 value, it means the mean and variance of the model are constant over time. So we retain the null hypotheses which assume that there is no heteroskedasticity.

3. Multicollinearity test using VIF test

Table 7: Multicollinearity test using VIF test

VIF	1/VIF
9.370	0.107
7.800	0.128
5.870	0.170
5.060	0.198
4.530	0.221
2.360	0.424
1.460	0.686
1.400	0.716
1.190	0.838
Mena VIF	4.070

Source: Author (2025)

Also, Multicollinearity test using VIF test, showed that since the mean VIF value is less than 10, it implies that there is absent of multicollinearity.

4. Discussion of Results

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effect of project governance structure on project success. The findings as presented above yield results which are in most cases not in line with already predicted expectations while to a lesser extent other move in line with expectation. This has prompted the researcher to give an explanation to back these findings.

The effect of project steering committee on the project success of Mideno in Bamenda was positive (+) and not significant. This research result was not in line with the results of Karlsen (2020) who "analysed how steering committees contribute to governance and trust on project outcome. Karlsen studied case concerns the Norwegian Navy's experience with a steering committee in the project of building new frigates. His findings show that the steering committee has a significant impact on governance and trust in the outcome of project. The identified governance mechanisms performed by the steering committee included: control and performance measurement, support, decision-making, relationship management, reporting, resource management, risk management and strategic focus. The analysis identifies composition, competence, authority, responsibility, commitment and continuity as steering committee features that contribute to building trust which will go through out every project to be successful like the case of Mideno in Bamenda. The insignificant effect of project steering committee on project success could be due to factors such as the composition of the committee, the level of engagement and oversight, or the decision-making processes

within the committee. So, the study gives a policy to develop a comprehensive resource management plan, implement robust monitoring and control mechanisms, and explore opportunities to optimize resource utilization, such as through resource sharing or leveraging new technologies.

The Effect of Project Manager on the Project Success of Miden in Bamenda was positive (+) and not significant. This research result is not in line with the results of Mulcahy (2018). Mulcahy "reassesses the relationship between project manager and project management success. The finding of this researcher shows that project manager plays a significant role in project management success. The result also explained that the capability of project manager on project team management, such as project activities planning, project team member skill evaluation and job distribution; knowledge on the application of project management tools and techniques; and how the project manager deals with political and cultural issues are the key elements for project success. As such, research studies have shown that the most capable and effective project managers have the ability to adapt their project management abilities to get the members demands of the project management team, stakeholders and specific requires in differ culture environments. The insignificant effect of project manager on project success could be due to factors such as the project manager's leadership skills, communication abilities, or their ability to coordinate and manage the project team and stakeholders. So committee members have the necessary expertise and decision-making authority, they should establish clear roles and responsibilities, encourage regular and effective communication with the project manager, and consider expanding the steering committee's involvement in key aspects of the project, such as risk management and strategic planning.

The Effect of project resource allocation on the project success of Miden in Bamenda was positive (+) and significant. This research result is in line with the results of Rugiri and Njangiru (2018). They studied the influence of resource allocation on water projects performance funded by Nyeri County, Kenya through CDF. The regression analysis results revealed that resource availability was a good predictor of project success. According to the findings of a Pearson correlation study, resource availability was positively related to project success. the positive sign on the coefficient of project resource allocation indicates that as the effectiveness of project resource allocation increases, project success tends to increase as well. The significant positive effect of project resource allocation on project success could be attributed to factors such as sound budgeting, efficient resource planning, and effective resource management practices. it is politicized to ensure that the project manager has the necessary skills, experience, and authority to lead the project, provide them with the necessary resources and support, establish clear communication channels and decision-making processes, and consider providing the project manager with additional training or mentorship to enhance their project management capabilities

5. Conclusion

A multiple linear regression was used in running the analysis; results showed that all the variables are having positive effect on project success. Despite being positive, project steering committee and project manager are insignificant except project resource

allocation that is significant. This give us a way to provide a valuable conclusion for the study.

Based on specific objective one, project steering committee has a positive and insignificant effect on project process. Therefore, we do not accept the alternative hypothesis, we retain the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect between project steering committee and project success of Miden0 in Bamenda.

Also, for specific objective two, project manager has a positive and insignificant effect on project process. Therefore, we do not accept the alternative hypothesis, we retain the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect between project manager and project success of Miden0 in Bamenda.

More so, for specific objective two, project resource allocation has a positive and significant effect on project process. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant effect between project steering committee and project success of Miden0 in Bamenda

Conclusively, according to the research it shows that the effect of project governance structure has a positive effect on project success for Miden0 in Bamenda.

1. Implications of the Study

The findings of this research have several practical implications. For project managers working in Miden0 Bamenda and comparable environments, the study underscores the importance of adopting effective governance structures to enhance project success. It demonstrates the value of clear oversight, strong accountability mechanisms, and well-defined decision-making processes in improving project outcomes. Policymakers can also draw on the study to design policies and guidelines that promote stronger governance practices, ultimately improving the execution of development projects in the region. Additionally, stakeholders including local communities, development partners, and beneficiaries, stand to benefit from the study's emphasis on transparency, accountability, and inclusive stakeholder engagement, all of which are essential for achieving sustainable and impactful project results.

2. Contributions to Science

This study makes significant contributions to scientific knowledge by providing empirical evidence on the effect of project governance structure on project success within the specific context of Miden0 Bamenda in the Northwest Region of Cameroon. By examining how governance mechanisms influence project outcomes, the study adds valuable data to the broader literature on project governance and project performance. It also offers context-specific insights by highlighting the unique challenges and opportunities associated with implementing project governance in Miden0 Bamenda. These contextual findings emphasize the importance of tailoring governance strategies to fit environmental and organizational realities. Furthermore, the results of the study have the potential to inform the development of a practical governance framework that can be applied in similar organizational and regional contexts, thereby strengthening theory and guiding future practice in project management.

3. Recommendations

1. **Prioritize Effective Resource Allocation:** The results showed that project resource allocation has a positive and significant effect on the project success of Miden0 in

Bamenda. This suggests that effectively managing and allocating resources, such as personnel, equipment, and funding, is crucial for the project's success. To achieve this, it is recommended to develop a comprehensive resource management plan, implement robust monitoring and control mechanisms, and explore opportunities to optimize resource utilization, such as through resource sharing or leveraging new technologies.

2. Strengthen the Project Steering Committee: While the results indicated that the project steering committee has a positive but insignificant effect on project success, it is still an important aspect of project governance. To enhance the impact of the steering committee, it is recommended to ensure that the committee members have the necessary expertise and decision-making authority, establish clear roles and responsibilities, encourage regular and effective communication with the project manager, and consider expanding the steering committee's involvement in key aspects of the project, such as risk management and strategic planning.

3. Empower the Project Manager: The results showed that the project manager has a positive but insignificant effect on project success. To leverage the project manager's role more effectively, it is recommended to ensure that the project manager has the necessary skills, experience, and authority to lead the project, provide them with the necessary resources and support, establish clear communication channels and decision-making processes, and consider providing the project manager with additional training or mentorship to enhance their project management capabilities.

4. Suggestions for Further studies

Future research could expand the understanding of project governance and project success by investigating additional factors that may influence outcomes in Mideno Bamenda, such as project manager competencies, team dynamics, leadership styles, and external environmental conditions. Comparative studies across different geographic or organizational contexts for example, urban versus rural settings or across various regions could also provide deeper insights into how governance structures function under varying circumstances. Longitudinal studies would be useful for examining how governance practices affect project success over time, offering a dynamic view of their long-term impact. Moreover, adopting mixed-methods approaches that integrate quantitative and qualitative data could enrich future analyses by providing a more holistic understanding of project governance and its effectiveness.

6. References

- Abu Hassim, A., Kajewski, S. & Trigunarsyah, B. 2011. The importance of project governance framework in project procurement planning. *Procedia Engineering*. 14,1929-1937.
- Amade, B., Ogbonna, A., & Kaduru, C. (2018). Determinants of successful project implementation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 1(6), 56 - 69
- Arora, M., & Baronikian, H. (2013), *Leadership in project management* (2nd ed). Canada: Leadership Publishing House.
- Association for Project Management (APM). 2009. *A Guide to the Governance Aspects of Project Sponsorship*.

- Bekker, M.C. & Steyn, H. 2009. Defining 'Project Governance' for Large Capital Projects. *South African Journal of Industrial Engineering* Vol 20(2), 81-92
- Bekker, M.C. 2014, Project Governance" "Schools of Thought", *South African Journal of Economic and Management Science*, Special Issue,17(2014), 22-32.
- Besong, D. K., et al. (2017). An empirical analysis of the impact of governance on project success in the construction sector in Cameroon. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 22(1), 39-58.
- Bevir, M., 2011. Governance as Theory, Practice, and Dilemma. In: M. Bevir, ed. *The SAGE Handbook of Governance*. (1st ed.). London: SAGE, 1-16.
- Blanco, I., Lowdens, V. & Pratchett, L., 2011. Policy Networks and Governance Networks: Towards Greater Conceptual Clarity. *Political Studies Review*, Volume 9, 297-308.
- Chipulu, M., Neoh, G., Ojiako, U., Williams, T. (2013), a multidimensional analysis of project manager competencies, *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, Vol. 60 No. 3, pp. 506-517.
- Christensen, C. M. (2013). *The innovator's dilemma: when new technologies cause great firms to fail*. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Crawford, L., & Pollack, J. (2004). *Hard and Soft Project Management: An Holistic and Human-Centred Approach*.
- Dietrich, F. & List, C. 2013. A Reason-Based Theory of Rational Choice. *Noûs*, 47(1), 104-134.
- Dow, W., Taylor, B. (2015). *Project management communication tools* (1st ed.). Dow Publishing LLC: Renton, WA.
- Dowding, K, 2011. Rational Choice Theory, in Bevir, M. ed, 2011. *Governance as Theory, Practice, and Dilemma*. The SAGE Handbook of Governance. (1st ed.). London: SAGE, 36-50.
- Gillibrand, M. 2004. New frontiers for corporate governance in 2004 and beyond. *Corporate Governance Journal*, 4(1), 4-21.
- Jeferson, A., Branco, B. V., Pereira, W., & Silveira. (2018), A Revaluation of the Criticality of the Project Manager to The Project's Success, *Business Management Dynamics* Vol.8, No.2, Aug 2018, pp.01-18.
- Kusi-Sarpong, S., et al. (2020). The Role of Governance in Achieving Sustainable Development in Africa: Evidence from Ghana. *Sustainability*, 12(18), 7392.
- Miller, R., & Lessard, D., 2000. eds, *The Strategic Management of Large Engineering Projects: Shaping Institutions, Risks, and Governance*, Massachusetts: Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Morris, P.W.G., & Gerald, J., 2011. Managing the institutional context for projects. *Project Management Journal*. 42(6), 20-32.

- Ochieng, E. A. (2018). *Influence of resource management on implementation of projects in global system of mobile communications companies in Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- OECD. 2004. Principles of corporate governance, France: OECD Publication Services. Oxford Dictionary Online. <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/English/governance?q=governance>
- Pemsel, S. & Muller, R. 2012. The governance of knowledge in project-based organizations. *International Journal of Project Management*. 30(8), 865-876.
- Penrose, E. T. (1959). *The Theory of the Growth of the Firm*. New York: John Wiley
- Pinto, J. K., & Slevin, D. P. (1988). Critical success factors across the project life cycle. *Project Management Journal*, 19(3), 67-75.
- Pinto, J. K., & Slevin, D. P. (2019). *Project management: achieving competitive advantage*. Pearson.
- PMBOK Guide. (2017). *A guide to the project management body of knowledge* (6th ed.). Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- PMI. (2021). *Governance of Portfolios, Programs, and Projects: A Practice Guide*.
- Prasad, S., Tata, J., Herlache, L., McCarthy, E. (2013), Developmental project management in emerging countries, *Oper. Manag. Res.* 6 (1-2), 53-73.
- Project Management Institute (2013). *A Guide to Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK); 4th Edition*.
- Project Management Institute (PMI). (2017). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK Guide)*.
- Project Management Institute Global Congress 2014 – North America.
- Radujkovića, S. (2017), *Project Management Success Factors*, Creative Construction Conference 2017, CCC 2017, 19-22 June 2017, Primosten, Croatia,
- Shenhar, A. J., & Dvir, D. (2007). *Reinventing project management: The diamond approach to successful growth and innovation*. Harvard Business Press.
- Snyder, C. (2012). *Manage to lead: Flexing your leadership style*. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.
- Sorensen, E. & Torfing, J., 2009. Making Governance Networks Effective and Democratic through Metagovernance. *Public Administration*, 87(2), 234 - 258.
- Turner, J. (2014), *The Handbook of Project-based Management: Leading Strategic Change in Organizations*, 3th ed. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Turner, J. R. (2014). *The Handbook of Project-Based Management*.
- Verzuh, E. (2019). *The Fast Forward MBA in Project Management*.